

Students' Perspectives on E-Learning Preferences, Effectiveness, and Satisfaction: Evidence from a Nigerian Public University

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Abstract

About 45 million Nigerian students reportedly experienced a period of significant redundancy due to the closure of schools without alternative learning channels during the COVID-19 lockdown in 2020. During this period, the University of Medical Sciences Ondo, a typical public university in Nigeria, launched an e-learning facility for its undergraduate students. This paper explores the preference for e-learning, its perceived effectiveness, satisfaction, and other experiences of the University's undergraduates with the e-learning facility in a developing country. A total of 516 undergraduates participated in the survey. The findings revealed that Google Classroom and Zoom are functional tools for e-learning in low-resource settings, with the students completing typical learning activities through these platforms. While only a few students currently prefer e-learning to physical learning, a higher number perceived e-learning as effective and were satisfied with the platform for teaching and learning. However, reported challenges, such as high internet access costs and lecturers' low e-learning competence, hindered the students from fully enjoying and maximizing the e-learning experience. The study underscores the importance of holistic planning before e-learning deployment in developing countries and the preference for blended learning among undergraduates in similar environments.

Keywords: e-learning, higher education, undergraduates, Nigeria, Google Classroom, blended learning, developing countries

Introduction

Appropriate and maximal e-learning utilisation is still a dream in developing countries. This affected the ability of many institutions in these countries to academically engage the students during an emergency such as the 2019 coronavirus disease (COVID-19). In Nigeria – a developing country in West Africa, about 45 million students were reported to have experienced a period of significant redundancy due to the closure of schools without alternative learning channels during the COVID-19 lockdown (Education in Emergency Working Group, 2020). There is thus a need to explore experiences with e-learning at different educational levels in developing countries to understand existing gaps and update the literature for policymakers, funders and other stakeholders in the education sector to enhance e-learning utilization in these settings.

The University of Medical Sciences Ondo (UNIMED) is one of Nigeria's public tertiary institutions that launched an e-learning facility in response to the coronavirus disease lockdown and still uses the facility today. Following the declaration of the disease as a pandemic by the World Health Organisation in March 2020, academic activities in higher institutions across Nigeria and most parts of the world came to a halt. The National Universities Commission in Nigeria instructed all universities to shut down and discontinue all academic and administrative activities, in line with a public health advisory issued by the Nigeria Centre for Disease Control to curtail the spread of the novel virus. The disruption in teaching, learning, research and other activities created a significant gap in academic progress for undergraduates in Nigeria and other nations. This disruption was estimated to have impacted about 91% of the global student population (United Nations Education, 2020).

In many parts of the world, the closure of universities and other tertiary institutions was replaced with electronic learning (e-learning) through various online platforms and facilities deployed over the Internet (Radha et al., 2020). This was largely not the case in Nigeria, as most higher institutions completely closed with little or no plan for e-learning, especially in public institutions (Eze et al., 2021; Nwafor & Osuji, 2021). The overreliance on traditional, face-to-face classroom teaching and learning made the institutions unprepared for the kind of acute disruption occasioned by COVID-19, resulting in undergraduates' prolonged redundancy without academic engagements.

Before the pandemic, most Nigerian universities did not have an e-learning facility. Despite the copious literature that has emanated from the country on technology, the uptake of e-learning remains low. Many lecturers in the country “considered e-learning an add-on, as they

expressed inability to integrate e-learning into their present task and do not even have the time to do so” (Nwagwu, 2020). This could be the typical mindset of many faculties in developing countries about e-learning. The deployment of e-learning at the University of Medical Sciences (UNIMED), a government-owned institution in Ondo State, Nigeria, during the heat of the COVID-19 pandemic enabled the institution to complete the 2019/2020 academic year successfully in 2020 – a feat that most public tertiary institutions in Nigeria and many other developing countries country did not achieve. The economic, intellectual, and financial loss that results from having students lie idle in their homes for a long time is not an option for any reason (University of Medical Sciences Ondo, 2020). Exploring e-learning for higher education purposes in developing countries is a welcome development that should be planned on evidence from users’ preferences. Thus, this study explored undergraduates’ preferences, perceived effectiveness, satisfaction, and other experiences of the e-learning facility instituted in a developing country setting, with the University of Medical Sciences Ondo (UNIMED) as a case. The specific objectives are to:

1. Identify the frequency of use and applications deployed for e-learning among undergraduates at UNIMED Nigeria;
2. Ascertain the device types and Internet sources and cost used for e-learning by undergraduates at UNIMED Nigeria;
3. Determine the students’ activities, preferences and training for e-learning at UNIMED Nigeria and
4. Determine the perceived effectiveness, satisfaction and challenges with e-learning among undergraduates at UNIMED Nigeria.

Methodology

This study was designed as a quantitative descriptive survey. The study population comprised 2,350 undergraduate students at the University of Medical Sciences Ondo, Nigeria, who were invited – more than once – via the central university listserv to participate in the survey. Being in a public university and having experienced e-learning for more than two academic sessions, UNIMED undergraduates were considered appropriate samples for undergraduates in a typical Nigerian public university. Except for the freshmen who are still in their first year of experiencing e-learning, the undergraduates participated in the study voluntarily by completing a questionnaire deployed through Google Forms for data collection for the study. A total of 516 responses were received from the students. The data were analysed through descriptive

statistics, including tables, charts and frequency counts, to address the study objectives using SPSS version 24. The data was collected during the 2021/2022 academic session, focusing on the use of e-learning platforms during the previous two sessions of 2019/2020 and 2020/2021 at the University.

Results and Discussion

Respondents characteristics

As revealed in Table 1, the total number of respondents was 516, resulting in a 21.96% response rate. Most respondents (68.2%) were females, and most undergraduates (84.2%) were within the 16-21 age group. This demography confirms the similarity of UNIMED undergraduates with students from other public universities in Nigeria (Olasina & Kheswa, 2021), a typical developing country in Africa.

Table 1: Respondents' characteristics

Characteristics		N	%
Gender	Male	113	21.8
	Female	403	68.2
Age Group (in years)	< 16	5	1.0
	16 – 18	210	40.9
	19 – 21	225	43.9
	21 – 24	52	10.1
	> 24	21	4.1
Level of study	200	269	52.4
	300	104	20.3
	400	72	14.0
	500	54	10.5
	600	14	2.7

Frequency of use and applications deployed for E-learning

This study explores the experiences of undergraduates with an e-learning system launched following the global lockdown occasioned by the disruptive COVID-19 pandemic in a developing country setting. With more than two-thirds of the students using the platform either daily or 2-4 times per week (Figure 1) during the session, the e-learning platform enjoyed acceptable patronage by the students. Findings from Figure 2 revealed that Google Classroom was the primary application deployed for e-learning at UNIMED. Google Classroom is an

application within the Google Education suite that provides higher education institutions with open-source applications for various educational purposes.

Figure 1: Frequency of use of e-learning platform undergraduates

Previous studies have considered Google Classroom suitable for e-learning in educational institutions (Alim et al., 2021; Ventayen et al., 2018). Nevertheless, Harefa (2020) warned that Google Classroom may not be suitable for teaching all subjects because of some deficiencies observed in its use for e-learning among building engineering students; if not investigated, such inadequacy may lead to users' dissatisfaction with the platform. Google Classroom offers an open-source opportunity for institutions in low and middle-income countries to launch their e-learning platforms without associated software costs (Dash, 2019). Other applications reportedly used by undergraduates for e-learning are those that facilitate online meetings for live classes and instant messaging to ease class communication.

Figure 2: Applications used for e-learning

Devices and Internet Sources for E-learning

The modes of accessing the platform could have aided the high frequency of use of the e-learning platform among the respondents. The results show that most students own the device they used to connect to the platform (Figure 3) and do not depend on institutional or public Internet sources for e-learning (Figure 4). While ownership of Internet-enabled devices is common among Nigerian undergraduates, the students often prefer institutional or public Wi-Fi to access the Internet for e-learning due to data costs (Sayekti, 2018). Prohibitive out-of-pocket internet costs have been identified as one of the barriers to e-learning in developing countries (Ekenze et al., 2019; Olum et al., 2020). Considering this and other Internet shortcomings in developing countries, e-learning deployment in low- and middle-income countries should be considerably linked to Internet hotspots or other innovative solutions where students can access e-learning materials and save materials for offline usage.

Figure 3: E-learning device ownership among students

Figure 4: Internet source for e-learning

Furthermore, nearly 90 percent of the undergraduates surveyed reported that they used handheld devices (smartphone, iPad or tablet) most of the time when they connected to the e-learning platform (Figure 5). This is noteworthy for e-learning administrators in developing

countries, who must consider platform responsiveness across multiple devices while selecting or building e-learning applications for higher education students. Most of the time, undergraduates in developing countries use smartphones to access the Internet (Dhir et al., 2017; Ifeanyi & Chukwuere, 2018; Sarwar et al., 2020); therefore, the features and functionalities of e-learning facilities for undergraduates in developing countries have to be mobile friendly. The prevalent ownership of smartphones among undergraduates should encourage deploying e-learning for enhanced learning among higher education students in developing countries. With smartphones, students can connect to e-learning platforms anytime and anywhere.

Figure 5: Types of devices used for accessing e-learning platform

As indicated earlier, the Internet source is an important aspect of students' use of e-learning platforms. Typically, e-learning is deployed over the Internet – synchronously or asynchronously. However, access to the Internet in Nigeria and many other developing countries is still pricey and presently forms an obstacle to e-learning implementation in these countries (Adeoye et al., 2020). Findings in this study showed that about half of the respondents estimated their monthly expenditure on mobile Internet access for e-learning to be between 1,000 and 3,000 Nigerian Naira (equivalent to \$2.4 – \$7.2 as of January 2022), while nearly 90% of the rest spend more (Figure 6). This is uneconomical for undergraduates in a developing country such as Nigeria, where the majority of students in public universities come from families with low economic status (Olasina & Kheswa, 2021) and rarely have access to work-study schemes.

The prevailing Internet access rates in many developing countries could prompt undergraduates to avoid some academically relevant multimedia resources in order to minimise mobile data usage and stay within budget. With e-learning, undergraduate students are expected to learn from anywhere; therefore, institutional Internet sources (Wi-Fi) may not adequately cater to e-learning purposes, especially in situations where the students reside outside institutional

premises. Aside from institutional Wi-Fi, adequate provisions must be made to ensure undergraduates are not discouraged from using e-learning platforms because of prohibitive Internet access costs. Higher educational institutions in developing countries could partner with mobile network operators on specially designed low-cost mobile data plans for undergraduate students.

Figure 6: Estimated monthly expenditure (in Naira) to access the Internet for e-learning

Activities, preferences and training for e-learning

As shown in Figure 7, more than half of the students reported using the e-learning platform to take quizzes and tests (55.6%), attend live classes (69.7%), access learning materials (90.8%) and submit assignments (93.3%). An earlier study by Ifijeh et al. (2015) reported that undergraduates in another Nigerian university primarily use e-learning facilities “to download lecture notes.” These findings indicate that e-learning activities are modelled after traditional (face-to-face) learning activities. Nevertheless, only about 27 per cent of the respondents indicated a moderate to high preference for e-learning over traditional learning, and nearly half of the students do not have such a preference for e-learning (Figure 8). This could suggest that the frequency of use earlier reported may have occurred out of necessity or compulsion and not due to the student’s acceptance of the platform.

Figure 7: Activities carried out by students on UNIMED e-learning platform

Figure 8: Students' preference for e-learning over traditional (face-to-face) learning

Since undergraduates in developing countries, especially those in public institutions, may not have been exposed to e-learning before university admission, conscious efforts should be made to systematically introduce them to such platforms. Zaneldin et al. (2019) and Olum et al. (2020) reported undergraduates' preference for blended learning over outright e-learning or traditional learning. Similarly, Ahmed and Reddy (2020) found that most medical undergraduate students desire multiple learning styles by showing preference to “take and review class notes, study silently, use e-learning uploaded materials, interact in the class and learn a clinical skill by practising on a real patient rather than simulated patients or mannequins.”

The report of Tarteer et al. (2021) on some students' preference for face-to-face learning also coincides with the low preference for e-learning recorded among respondents in this study. However, nearly one-quarter of the students are almost undecided, indicating that they “somehow preferred” (Figure 8). This finding could align with some reports showing that e-learning alone does not significantly affect students' knowledge of a subject (McDonald et al., 2018; Mehta et al., 2016). However, other reports of improved academic performance are due to e-learning deployment among undergraduates (Bennett et al., 2014; Tashkandi, 2021).

In developing countries such as Nigeria, for undergraduates to appreciate e-learning facilities and maximise the benefits of e-learning, the need for enlightenment and training before e-

learning deployment in any institution should be prioritized (Elbasuony et al., 2018). In this study, most of the responses indicated that the undergraduates did not get adequate user training before the launch of the e-learning platform (Figure 9). At the same time, about the same ratio of students reported being provided with a guide (user manual) for the e-learning platform. The lack of training while introducing undergraduates to such technology could affect the students' acceptance, preference and utilization of the platform.

Figure 9: Types of training provided before e-learning deployment

Perceived effectiveness, satisfaction, and challenges with e-learning facility

When asked about their perception of the effectiveness of the e-learning platform for teaching and learning, about one-third of the respondents found the e-learning platform to be moderately or highly effective for teaching and learning purposes (Figure 10a). Most students were unsure about its effectiveness based on their rating of “somehow effective.” Similar statistics were obtained for students' level of satisfaction with the e-learning platform (Figure 10b). This could indicate a correlation between the undergraduates' perceived effectiveness and satisfaction with the e-learning platform. An earlier report by Kaur et al. (2020) showed similar findings where students rated e-learning as effective in some aspects and ineffective in others. Similarly, a nationwide study of undergraduate Dentistry students in Pakistan also reported students' dissatisfaction with online learning and the level of teachers' skills for e-learning (Sarwar et al., 2020).

(a)

(b)

Figure 10: (a) Students' perceived effectiveness of e-learning platform; and (b) students' satisfaction with e-learning platform for teaching and learning (Source: the authors)

Furthermore, most undergraduate respondents in this study consider some of their lecturers' attitudes challenging for e-learning. The students noted inadequate explanation of topics as one of the barriers to e-learning and indicated that lecturers utilized the platform to bombard them with learning materials (Figure 11). While technological innovations often encounter teething problems when launched in developing countries, every institution should seek to identify challenges from e-learning users and work towards ameliorating them. Other challenges to e-

learning, as reported by more than 50 per cent of the undergraduates, include poor internet service, unstable power supply and high data consumption (Figure 11), some of which are typical barriers to internet-based technologies in the developing world. Similar challenges have been reported by Dumbiri and Nwadiani (2020) and Goodluck et al. (2015) among Nigerian undergraduates. Power outages pose significant challenge to e-learning in developing countries. Nevertheless, modern smartphones are improving with battery life, which could be leveraged appropriately while the challenge lasts.

Figure 11: Challenges encountered with e-learning

Conclusion

This study was carried out to explore the perception, perceived effectiveness, satisfaction and other experiences of undergraduate students with the e-learning platform in a developing country setting – University of Medical Sciences Ondo as a case. The findings implicated the need for holistic planning before deploying e-learning for undergraduates. From this study, it becomes clear that undergraduates do not presently prefer e-learning over physical classroom learning but would use e-learning platforms when necessary. The students were satisfied with their e-learning experience and fairly perceived its effectiveness in teaching and learning.

However, if unaddressed, identified challenges could affect the quality of education they receive through e-learning.

The study concludes that e-learning platforms can support the actualization of important academic activities in higher educational institutions in developing countries. Increasing students' ownership of smartphones and other handheld devices is leveraged for e-learning deployment in developing country settings.

Recommendations

1. Universities in developing countries should adopt blended learning when possible so that undergraduates can better appreciate and maximize the benefits of e-learning.
2. Students and faculties must be properly enlightened and trained on e-learning to ensure their full buy-in and maximum utilization.
3. Innovative, low-cost Internet access schemes should be deployed for e-learning among undergraduates in developing countries.
4. While Google Classroom suffices for basic e-learning activities, software evaluation should be conducted to compare it with other e-learning platforms to improve student satisfaction and perception of effectiveness.

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